

XROTOR

X-shaped Radical Offshore Wind Turbine for Overall Cost of Energy Reduction

D7.6

Output of Attribute Matching

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 @XROTORProject

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About X-ROTOR

X-ROTOR: “X-shaped Radical Offshore wind Turbine for Overall cost of energy Reduction” is a Horizon 2020 funded project which aims to develop a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept.

The X-ROTOR project is led by University of Strathclyde (UK) in partnership with Norwegian University of Science and Technology (Norway), Delft University of Technology (Netherlands), University College Cork (Ireland), Fundacion Cener National Renewable Energy Centre (Spain) and GE Renovables España (Spain).

As the effects of climate change are becoming ever more visible, Europe has raised its target for the amount of energy it consumes from renewable sources from the previous goal of 27% to 32% by 2030. Offshore wind energy can play a key role in achieving the EU target and contribute to the required 40% reduction in CO₂ emissions. However, to achieve the previously mentioned targets the cost of offshore wind must be reduced. The X-ROTOR concept provides a direct route to drastically reducing both capital and operating costs of energy from offshore wind.

The project runs for three years from January 2021, during which time, the concept will be developed through a holistic consideration of technical, cost, environmental and socio-economic impact aspects.

If proven feasible, X-ROTOR will, as a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept, create new opportunities for the European wind energy industry and play an important role maintaining the EU’s position as global technological leader in renewable energy, reducing greenhouse gas emissions and decarbonising the EU economy.

For more information see <https://xrotor-project.eu>

Description of the deliverable and its purpose

The X-ROTOR project is developing an innovative turbine design for off-shore wind deployment, with the aim of reducing both costs and installation times, and in so doing contributing to an increase in off-shore deployment. This report uses data collected through the project's continuing engagement with industry stakeholders to identify and rank attributes important for potential purchasing decisions in which these stakeholders may have input. The attributes identified from the collected stakeholder data are compared with the features of the X-ROTOR derived from an analysis of the foundational overview text, which first described the concept. In this way the report assesses the extent to which the developing X-ROTOR design addresses those attributes which the industry stakeholders have deemed important to them.

List of acronyms

AHP	Analytic Hierarchy Process
ASD	Asynchronous Structured Dialogue
DoA	Description of Action
GHG	Greenhouse gas
HAWT	Horizontal axis wind turbine
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
LCOE	Levelised cost of energy
O&M	Operation and Maintenance
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
OREC	Ocean Renewable Energy Coalition
PCM	Pairwise Comparison Matrix
SSPs	Shared socio-economic pathways
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
VAWT	Vertical axis wind turbine
WESC	Wind Energy Science Conference
WP	Work Package
XRC	X-ROTOR concept

1 Introduction

This deliverable aims to assess the degree to which the developing X-ROTOR concept meets the needs of potential buyers; it does this by comparing the features or attributes considered important by industry stakeholders with the features of the X-ROTOR design.

1.1 Background

The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) issues evaluation reports that represent the most thorough and recent assessments of our society's progress toward catastrophic climate change. In April of 2022, they released the third part of their sixth evaluation report, and it contains the direst warnings yet of the need to drastically reduce our carbon emissions now or suffer certain environmental disaster. The report lays out five different scenarios, called shared socio-economic pathways (SSPs), and only one of them (SSP1) describes a trajectory that will keep the Earth's average temperature from rising 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels thereby avoiding the worst effects of anthropogenic climate change (IPCC, 2022).

The emissions reductions called for in SSP1 are substantial. Society needs to eliminate all greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions by 2050, eliminating half of them by 2030 (IPCC, 2022). WindEurope¹ argues in its 2019 report that to become carbon neutral by 2050, Europe must have about 450 GW of offshore wind power installed that will meet about 30% of Europe's electricity demand. This demand is 50% higher than in 2015 due to the electrification of the transport and heat sectors that must also take place by this time for European society to be carbon neutral. In 2019, Europe had 20 GW of offshore wind power meeting about 1.5% of electricity demand and was adding about 3 GW a year. To hit a total of 450 GW by 2050 (starting in 2020) would require a pace of about 15 GW installed each year, a five-fold increase (Freeman *et al.*, 2019). Further, the European Commission is planning an even more aggressive roll out of renewable energy development to combat the influence of Russian gas imports on the continent's economy – by proposing an additional €210 billion to increase deployment (Rankin, 2022).

The team behind the X-ROTOR turbine concept asked if there are design innovations that can be made to the standard wind turbine design to bring its costs down and shorten installation times – so that the industry could increase its pace of production. What they developed is a radical new type of wind turbine, one suited particularly well to mass production, quick installation, floating foundation deployment, and more favourable levels of public acceptance (Leithead *et al.*, 2019). This new turbine design could not come at a better time. The offshore wind industry is still new enough that there is not a prohibitive amount of coalescence around a single design and that there is still room for a disruptive technology to take hold.

1.2 The X-ROTOR concept

At first glance, this turbine design looks unusual. It looks like a vertical axis wind turbine (VAWT), but the air foils are not what one might expect to find on VAWT. They are not as proportionately wide and do not have as pronounced a curve. The X-ROTOR concept borrows this design feature from what is known as the Taylor V-VAWT² (Robotham *et al.*, 1986), but it adds some new features. The innovation to this design comes with

¹ WindEurope is an association of over 600 members, which promotes the use of wind power in Europe.

² Also known as the Sharpe V-VAWT. Sharpe and Taylor (1985) co-authored the original conference paper presenting the idea.

the addition of two, lower transverse blades giving the structure its “X” appearance. These blades reduce the overturning moment, and they provide a support for the secondary rotors. These secondary rotors provide the power take-off in much the same way as with traditional horizontal axis wind turbines (HAWT) except that they are smaller, turn much faster, and are only located about 25 metres above the ocean surface. The rotation on the vertical axis increases the speed of the wind encountered by these HAWTs. Because the tip speed ratio of the vertical blades is 4:1, with the tip speed ratio of the blades on the horizontal axis also 4:1, that means these secondary rotors are spinning at a 16:1 ratio, or 160 m/s – 180 m/s. These secondary rotors can also control the speed of the vertical axis, maximizing aerodynamic efficiency at below cut-in speeds and controlling rotational speed at above rated wind speeds to keep the vertical rotation constant (Leithead *et al.*, 2019). So, in a very real sense, the X-ROTOR offers a hybrid of both vertical and horizontal turbines, keeping the best of both design types and leaving the rest. Figure 1 below presents an approximation of how the concept will appear.

Figure 1: Representations³ of the X-ROTOR concept (Carroll & Dunphy, 2021, p. 2)

1.3 Structure of the report

The report is divided into four sections as outlined below:

- 1 – *Introduction*: presents an overview of the report including its aims, details the background to the work, provides context for the task undertaken, and presents the structure of the document.
- 2 – *Information gathering*: describes how the information was collected through engagement with stakeholders, review of literature and an analysis of the X-ROTOR concept foundational document.
- 3 – *Results*: presents the findings from the stakeholders’ results arising from, identification of attributes desired by potential buyers and matching them to the features of the X-ROTOR concept.
- 4 – *Discussions and conclusions*: discusses the attributes matching process, summarises the key findings of the report and offers some concluding statements.

³ There is also a three-blade design for the vertical axis rotor.

2 Information Gathering

The public health restrictions put in place during the initial intense phases of the COVID 19 pandemic necessitated a pivot in engagement strategies during the first year of the study. The traditional face-to-face workshops which were no longer permitted were replaced with so-called asynchronous structured dialogues with participants from both Group 1 (societal stakeholders) and Group 2 (industry stakeholders). This process, which involved the remote delivery of structured questionnaires proved a very successful form of engagement. The methodology and survey design for exploring the attributes of offshore wind turbines which influence potential purchasing decision was outlined in D7.5 Final Survey Design and Methodology (Deeney and Dunphy, 2021a).

The asynchronous structured dialogues with the societal stakeholders (associated with coastal communities in Ireland Spain and the United Kingdom) consisted of several statements (albeit differing in the language used) to which respondents were invited to indicate the extent to which they agreed or disagreed with them⁴, as well as some open-ended, nonspecific questions aimed at gauging opinions of, and support for, offshore wind turbines and encouraging them to be expansive in their responses (Deeney and Dunphy, 2021b, p. 6). The participants were asked a series of general questions to ascertain their perceptions of, and opinion on, offshore wind energy in general. This is important because although participants in this group are not as knowledgeable about turbine specifics, they do know what they like or do not like about wind energy and it will be people from this group, writ large, who determine whether a project based on this new design will gain acceptability in the community or not (Lundheim *et al.*, 2022).

The engagement with Group 2 participants (academics and wind energy professionals) focused on technical aspects and enquired what they would like to see in any new turbine design. As it will generally be these professional individuals who will influence purchasing decisions. The approach detailed more fully in D7.5 envisaged a multi-step, iterative process combining a SWOT Analysis, sequencing exercise and an analytic hierarchy process (AHP) will be used within the context of an asynchronous structured dialogue.

The first step involved the use of a SWOT analysis to encourage critical thinking regarding wind turbine design. The second step comprised a modified Delphi study consisting of two elements based on the criteria used to judge the suitability of turbines. The first element a sequencing exercise, the second is a pairwise comparison feeding into an analytic hierarchy process, resulting in a ranked sequence of attributes.

Engaging the industrial stakeholders for these surveys proved challenging – the response rate, while passable, was not as good as envisaged. It is therefore intended to continue the sequencing exercise and conduct the pairwise comparison in the first quarter 2023. For this report, the methodology was followed in an amended fashion, with the analytic hierarchy process postponed and the ranked attributes determined after the sequencing exercise. An updated iteration of the attribute matching will be provided with D7.7 Report on economic impact.

⁴ Using a Likert score (scoring 1–5: Strongly disagree; Disagree; Neither agree/disagree; Agree; Strongly Agree).

3 Results

3.1 Findings from engagements

The researchers took notes on their conversations with both Group 1 and Group 2 participants outside of the specific survey questions to retrieve their general feelings about climate change and wind energy. They chose to use word clouds to immediately and visually convey this information. The differences were stark in that community members tended to have more broad concerns whereas industry experts focussed almost entirely on issues of cost as illustrated by the two ‘word cloud’ presented as Figure 2 and Figure 3 below.

Figure 2: ‘Word Cloud’ of societal stakeholders’ concerns

From Figure 2 above one can see that though the societal stakeholders generally see wind turbines as good, they have other concerns associated with fishing, the area chosen for development, reducing the cost of electricity, and the community in general. Whereas the industry respondents below were more interested in cost and the technical details that would influence costs.

Figure 3: ‘Word Cloud’ of industry stakeholders’ concerns

In response to the specific surveys, the two groups align a little more closely in that at the top attributes of wind turbines that both groups would like to see both focus on economic concerns, though, as might be imagined, the specific costs and benefits are different for each group.

3.1.1 Societal stakeholder findings

Figure 4 below depicts societal stakeholder's level of agreement on topic questions in their survey. A score of 1 would indicate that all the members of the group agree with the adjacent statement. A score of -1 would indicate that all the members of the group disagree with the adjacent statement.

Figure 4: Group 1 Agreement Scores for Topics (Deeney and Dunphy, 2021b, p. 12)

The societal stakeholders (Group 1 participants) felt overwhelmingly that offshore wind farms were a good thing for society and there was a strong majority that felt an offshore wind farm would not damage the leisure and tourism industries. The group was closely split on whether the farms would pose a serious problem for fishing, whether they would disturb wildlife, and whether they would kill seabirds, with a slight majority disagreeing with each statement. There was more agreement against the proposition that wind turbines are noisy. There was agreement that a windfarm would provide jobs for the community and decrease the community's cost for electricity.

To better understand the meaning of these results, a review was conducted of other surveys directed at the general public's opinions about offshore wind energy development. This was not intended as a comprehensive literature review⁵, but rather an attempt to see how the results of our survey matched up with other similar surveys conducted since 2015 (one 2009 source was chosen because it centred on coastal zone user groups just like ours does). Starting with this study, the authors cite "visual disamenities" as the number one concern for coastal users. In fact, coastal users expressed a willingness-to-pay preference of twice the cost of near shore turbines to have the turbines located out of view from the shore – a distance estimated at 50km from shore⁶ (Ladenburg and Dubgaard, 2009, p. 234). In 2009, there were no offshore wind farms that were 50km from shore or more. In 2020, construction on Hornsea One began and it is located 120km from the UK shores (Unwin, 2020).

Though there were no questions specifically about distance from shore on our survey, the question regarding the damage to leisure and tourism was meant to capture this issue by drawing a direct link between tourism and the visual impact of the turbines in the water. More than two-thirds of the respondents did not think that tourism or leisure activities would be damaged. This conclusion is also

⁵ For a more detailed literature review on OWE acceptance, see (Lundheim et al., 2022)

⁶ 50km is an outlier. Most studies put this limit at about 42km or less depending upon the size of the turbines and the farm. An authoritative study on this issue is (Sullivan et al., 2013).

supported by an article specifically on tourists’ attitudes toward offshore wind energy (OWE) development. The authors of this paper found that there is a misapprehension regarding the negative attitude toward OWE. Participants were asked what they thought were the opinions of others regarding OWE and the results are interesting. Regardless of whether the respondent was for or against OWE, both groups grossly overestimated the negative feelings about OWE among their peers (Westerberg, Jacobsen and Lifran, 2015). This result was repeated in Sokoloski, Markowitz and Bidwell (2018). Bush & Hoagland discovered in their analysis of public opinion surrounding the Rock Island offshore wind farm off Rhode Island’s coast that the more residents learned of the project, the more they grew to accept it. This result led to their conclusion that early public engagement can help alleviate challenges to OWE development (2016).

Brownlee, *et al.*, found that the strongest opposition to OWE based upon visual disamenities was found among marine recreationists. The authors found that this group of coastal users often develop strong emotional and cognitive associations with the marine environment because of their repeated activities in one location. Interestingly, this opposition was not dominant with citizens who lived near the ocean but in a location where there was a dearth of recreational opportunities and where there may be several industrial activities already taking place (2015). Devine-Wright and Howes attributed this difference to residents’ perceptions of whether an OWE project was a “good fit” for the environment (2010, p. 272).

Klain *et al.* (2018) explored the perception of ecosystem risks associated with offshore wind farm deployment in New Zealand. Figure 5 below shows their concerns relation to offshore wind farms. Of course, citizen concerns vary according to local specificities. For instance, the level of concern for the impact on the environment and specifically wildlife reported in this study was not replicated in our surveys. Similarly, while Klain *et al.* (2018) report ‘property values’ at the very bottom of their list, a study in North Carolina, USA by Gonyo *et al.*, (2021) ranked it as the issue of most concern. Such differences support Devine-Wright and Wiersma’s (2020, p. 3) argument for ‘research into community acceptance of offshore wind energy that takes account of the diverse meanings associated with place and technology in island socio-cultural contexts.’

Figure 5: Offshore Wind Farm Concerns (Klain *et al.*, 2018, p. 117)

3.1.2 Industry stakeholder findings

Figure six below presents the mean level of importance industry experts assigned to different criteria they would use in selection of a new wind turbine design. A score of 3 indicated that the stated attribute was very important, a score of 2 meant that it was important, and a score of 1 meant that the attribute was of low importance. If the respondent did not know how important they considered the attribute, they were instructed to score it a zero.

Figure 6: Level of Importance of Different Criteria from Group 2 (Deeney and Dunphy, 2021b, p. 13)

From the results presented above it is clear that direct and indirect financial considerations are at the top of industry experts' concerns. The first seven criteria in the ranking all have this topic as their main area of concern (survivability, #2, and power capacity, #7, both deal with quantity of power production, i.e., asset loss and income). Though the effect on local people ranks #8, concerns about the financial impact on those people rank 13, 16, 17, 18, and 19 – out of 19 attributes (visibility, noise, and scenery impact all related to the desirability of the locale as a tourist destination and/or to the impact on coastal property values). It is not terribly surprising that industry experts would value the economic criteria as the most important, but that the potential negative economic impact on the local population should be so disregarded is a little surprising. It is, however, not out of line with other surveys of industry experts and practitioners about OWE.

In our review of other surveys of offshore wind energy professionals, their concerns were universally skewed toward economic and technical concerns. Environmental and local acceptability issues appeared much lower on their list of concerns, if at all. On this last point, in the article by Loughney *et al.* which used a similar survey method to that in this study – multiple-attribute decision-analysis – there was no mention

of any variables related to community acceptability, though there was mention of some environmentally related attributes (2021).

In the surveys of industry experts and practitioners by Beiter *et al.* (2022) and Deveci *et al.* (2020), community perception and environmental concerns did get a mention, but like in our survey⁷, these concerns were lower on their list of priorities. The survey by Beiter *et al.* focused on what these professionals thought about the future of the wind industry and with regards to future offshore turbine design. Using “growth in turbine size” as an indicator of future development. As shown in Figure 7 the study found local community concerns were consider the second lowest of factors (Beiter *et al.*, 2022).

Offshore wind: factors that may limit future growth in turbine size	No impact (0) ↔ Large impact (3)
Vessels: Vessel capabilities and costs	2.3
Cranes: Lifting / crane capabilities and costs	2.2
Ports: Port capabilities and costs	2.2
Design/materials: Design and materials constraints, leading to high costs	1.9
Permitting: Siting and permitting regulations and requirements	1.8
Transportation: Transportation (e.g., bridge clearances) limitations and costs	1.5
Community: Local community concerns	1.3
Risk: Increased risk given larger impact associated with failure of single turbine	1.2

Figure 7: Factors Limiting Growth of Turbine Size (Beiter *et al.*, 2022, p. 1368)

The survey by Deveci *et al.* compiled a list of 42 attributes from the literature regarding the selection of sites for a new offshore wind farm (hypothetical). In looking at the attributes that experts thought were very important, 9 out of 34 did think that community acceptance was very important. This variable ranked eighth on the list for having an expert think that it was very important⁸. Though that seems fairly positive from a community interest perspective, if we look closer at the variables which would likely feed into community acceptance, it appears that these experts have a more abstract view of acceptance as revealed by the low numbers of experts who assigned a high importance value to any of the other more concrete variables that would affect acceptability. The table below puts this into perspective.

Criteria	Number selecting as very import
Proximity to the shore (noise, visual impact, <i>etc.</i>)	3
Proximity to a land protection area	1
Effects of wind farm on marine life	5
Proximity to passage route of birds	3
Economic externalities (costs or benefits incurred by a third party)	2
Local economic benefits (employment)	2
Community/local acceptance	9

Table 1: Criteria classified as very important by experts (Adapted from Deveci *et al.*, 2020, p. 110926)

⁷ It does not appear that the experts were asked about these concerns by the authors who were focused only on the technical and financial aspects of offshore floating wind turbines. The omission is still important in that the authors, presumably industry experts themselves though probably not practitioners, did not think these concerns were important enough to ask about.

⁸ Note respondents were not limited in the number of criteria they could claim was very important. So, the fact that only roughly one-quarter thought to consider it so is telling.

As we see from this table, though 9 experts cite community acceptance as very important, only a handful (less than 3 except for on 1 criterion which had 5) thought any of the specific criteria that might relate to community acceptability deserved a “very important” rating. These results are similar to that found in our own attribute matching exercise.

3.2 Attribute Matching

Determining the preferences for a new offshore wind turbine from experts in the field was a relatively straight forward process. As mentioned in section 2.1, the point of the survey for Group 2 participants was for them to go through a multi-step, iterative process (Delphi Cycle) that would lead to a hierarchical list of criteria, more or less consensus derived, upon which to evaluate the usefulness of the X-ROTOR design for their portfolio of options in building out their assets.

To determine what characteristics of the X-ROTOR concept matched these industry experts’ opinions, we conducted a thematic analysis of an article by the initiator of the X-ROTOR concept. This peer reviewed article entitled ‘*The X-ROTOR Offshore Wind Turbine Concept*’ (Leithead *et al.*, 2019), presents a thorough and detailed account of the proposed design advantages of this concept. As this idea is still in the conceptual phases, it represents an opportune time to incorporate the perspectives of industry experts so that the innovators can heed what the potential buyers want most to see from this new design.

Thematic analysis “is a rather basic, flexible tool. At the heart of it lies a process called coding: the gradual development of labels and their application to segments of potentially relevant data” (Herzog, Handke and Hitters, 2019, p. 3). A two-pronged approach was used to develop this categorization in line with the guidelines of Clarke and Braun (2014). First, following an inductive process, the text was approached fresh and coded according to the different themes found within. Eighteen different themes were found in the text. From this list, 12 themes were extracted corresponding to what could reasonably be called attributes of the X-ROTOR. Then the Leithead *et al.* text was revisited and operating on the basis that the frequency of attribute correlated to the level of importance the authors attributed to that specific attribute, two lists were developed. One was a list from the survey of the potential attributes industry experts would like to see addressed by any new turbine design ranked from 1 to 14 (the last four were dropped as the description of activities for this project asked that we only consider those survey categories that fell within the first four quintiles, the top 80%. It is not a logical necessity that the more mentions of a theme correlate to the level of importance placed on it by the authors. Without a list by the authors themselves regarding their ranking of attributes, this approach stands as a proxy for what is likely the relative importance of each attribute. This added specification, number of occurrences, is just meant to show how closely the text’s treatment of the attributes correlates to what experts in the field hold as most important. There were only two attributes that ranked high on one list and low on the other. For the purposes of matching the X-ROTOR attributes to the survey responses, however, it is, strictly speaking, not necessary to rank the attributes by number of occurrences. It is only necessary to show that a correlation between what experts think of as a valuable attribute is captured by the fleshed-out description of the turbine’s concept.

Survey	Attributes from Yr1 Group 2 survey	X-ROTOR features (Leithead <i>et al.</i> , 2019)	Frequency of Occurrence
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Rank				
1	LCOE		Survivability	1
2	Survivability		Secondary rotors	2
3	Installation costs		Reduced LCOE	3
4	Operation and Maintenance costs		O&M costs	4
5	Purchase costs		Turbine costs	5
6	Choice of power capacity		Direct drive, no gearbox	6
7	Effect on people		Floating platform poss.	7=
8	Effect on wildlife		Up-scalability	7=
9	Onshore requirements		Power capacity	9
10	Height		Reduced primary rotor size	10
11	Bird collisions		Noise	11=
12	Impact on fishing		Local jobs	11=
13	Fixed or floating			
14	Effect on radio/radar		Not mentioned	

Figure 8 below depicts the results of our attribute matching exercise. Some survey results correlate to more than one attribute and, likewise, some attributes fulfil the needs of more than one preference from the expert survey.

Survey Rank	Attributes from Yr1 Group 2 survey	X-ROTOR features (Leithead <i>et al.</i> , 2019)	Frequency of Occurrence
1	LCOE	Survivability	1
2	Survivability	Secondary rotors	2
3	Installation costs	Reduced LCOE	3
4	Operation and Maintenance costs	O&M costs	4
5	Purchase costs	Turbine costs	5
6	Choice of power capacity	Direct drive, no gearbox	6
7	Effect on people	Floating platform poss.	7=
8	Effect on wildlife	Up-scalability	7=
9	Onshore requirements	Power capacity	9
10	Height	Reduced primary rotor size	10
11	Bird collisions	Noise	11=
12	Impact on fishing	Local jobs	11=
13	Fixed or floating		
14	Effect on radio/radar	Not mentioned	

Figure 8: Attribute matching – industry stakeholder group and X-ROTOR features (from Leithead *et al.* 2019)

Some attributes mentioned by industry groups but with low ranking (visibility, impact on shipping, noise output, and impacts on scenery) were not included in this exercise as they fell within the fifth quintile, *i.e.*, they were not in the top 80% of responses regarding characteristics though to be most important for a new turbine design.

4 Discussion and Conclusion

4.1 Discussion

A lower **LCOE**, levelised cost of energy, was the number one characteristic of a new turbine that the industry participants wanted to see actualized. A reduced LCOE ranked as the third most frequently mentioned attribute of the X-ROTOR design in the Leithead *et al.* article. It could easily have ranked #1 if mentions of capital and O&M costs, two of the greater contributions to an LCOE, were considered as components of the LCOE. It was decided to keep them as separate mentions as there are unique aspects of both O&M and capital costs that also correlate to those topics in the survey. Overall, Leithead *et al.* estimate that the LCOE of the X-ROTOR will be 22% - 26% less than traditional HAWT offshore turbines (2019, p. 10).

Survivability was the second most agreed upon characteristic of a new offshore wind turbine that the industry group would like to see addressed. It is no wonder since a developer could stand substantial amounts of money if something goes significantly wrong with the turbines while out in the middle of the ocean (Ioannou, Angus and Brennan, 2020; Li, Díaz and Guedes Soares, 2021). Survivability ranked number one on the list of X-ROTOR attributes. Though the article does cover survivability in extreme weather events, most of the mentions of survivability deal with the structural analysis of the blades and the various loads the structure as a whole will have to endure.

Installation costs ranked third on the industry survey. Though the article does not specifically mention installation costs, there is an attribute that is discussed which has a direct bearing on installation costs. This attribute is the reduced size and weight (10th on the list of X-ROTOR attributes). With the reduced weight, there is less need for a heavy lift vessel which comprises a significant portion of the installation costs (Sarker and Faiz, 2017). Likewise, the lower weight also reduces the floating foundation construction costs and the costs associated with transporting and installing the structure (Sergiienko *et al.*, 2022). Related to installation costs, but not directly stated in the article, is the structure's **height** (11th most important characteristic on the expert survey). From the information provided (secondary rotor hub height of 20m, upper foil 100m, lower foil 65m, conical angles 30° and 50° respectively – p.5) it appears that the structure's height is currently designed to be around 120.5 meters above sea level⁹. That is about half as tall as a Vestas 6.2 MW turbine (Vestas, no date)¹⁰.

Operation and Maintenance (O&M) costs were the fourth most important characteristic of a new turbine design according to our industry group survey. There were 9 different discussions of O&M costs in the Leithead article ranking it number 4 on the list of attributes. Because the secondary rotors are smaller and closer to the surface of the ocean, their repair does not require expensive lift boats and they could even be

⁹ $20\text{m} + [\sin(50) \times 65\text{m}] + [\sin(30) \times 100\text{m}] = 120.5\text{m}$

¹⁰ Hub height, 170m, swept area, 20,612m². So, $r = 81\text{m} + 170\text{m} = 251\text{m}$

removed and replaced with a spare reducing the time at sea for the repair. Furthermore, there is a specific attribute of the design which reduces maintenance costs. X-ROTOR does not have a gearbox and has direct drive instead (6th most mentioned attribute). Though there may be more expensive repairs to an offshore wind turbine, few entail as much downtime as repairing a faulty gearbox (Carroll *et al.*, 2017), and time is money, especially if the asset is not producing any revenue while the repair takes place. All of these factors equate to a 55% reduction in O&M costs compared to a traditional offshore wind turbine (Leithead *et al.*, 2019, p. 10).

Purchase costs fall next on the survey. We correlate that characteristic to the lower turbine costs of the X-ROTOR design. Leithead *et al.* estimate that because there is no gearbox and because the structure itself is smaller and requires no special forming of the blades for any of the three rotors, the turbine should be about 32% less costly than traditional HAWTs of the same power rating (2019, p. 10).

Choice of power capacity ranked sixth on the expert list of preferences. There were three themes in the article which aligned with this option. There were two occurrences of power capacity in general terms and of the X-ROTOR's current design capacity, 6.47 MW with winds at 12.5 m/s. The possibility of up scaling this capacity was raised at three different points in the paper with the conclusion that it was possible to approach the contemporary output of the larger offshore wind turbines being installed today. A side note here not mentioned in the article is that there is an interesting option to increase the power output per square km of sea surface. Though the current design of the X-ROTOR is for a nameplate capacity of 6.47 MW, the nature of the way this turbine extracts energy from the wind allows for two turbines to be placed close together and just have one spinning clockwise and the other counter-clockwise. In this configuration, two VAWTs placed side by side and close to each other will increase the power production of the pair more than the sum of each acting independently of the others wake (Vergaerde *et al.*, 2020), and so a farm of X-ROTORS can have twice as many turbines as a farm of HAWTs of the same size and produce more power per square km of ocean area. The third attribute matched to a choice on power capacity comes from the 14 mentions of the secondary rotors.

The 2nd-place ranking of the theme of the two secondary rotors is not unusual given that this aspect of the X-ROTOR is what really makes it stand apart from other VAWTs. The power take-offs are located at each rotor and can be increased by increasing the swept area of the blades or by adding a third rotor on an additional third crossbar/vertical blade section of the turbine. Both these options are currently being explored by engineers on the project.

It is not until the seventh category that potential social impacts of the turbine are raised. The **effect on people** is not a focus of the Leithead *et al.* article. There is one tangential reference to creating local jobs (the possibility of local boats providing transportation and local ports offering quay-side maintenance and staging areas) in the article (Leithead *et al.*, 2019, p. 3). Though the article does not mention fishing jobs directly, thoughts about the local job market and reduced fishing areas naturally leads the reader to wonder about the connection between X-ROTOR and commercial fisheries. Despite the common perception that wind farms have a negative impact on **fishing** (Gray, Haggatt and Bell, 2005), offshore wind farms could actually provide additional habitat for sea life and thereby contribute to the health of the fishery (Wilson and Elliott, 2009).

The **effect on wildlife** was the 8th most important characteristic for our wind energy experts. The article does not answer the wildlife question directly as research into the concept is currently examining such interactions, but it does mention (once) that this turbine will be pretty loud because the secondary rotors are spinning with tip speeds of up to 180 m/s. Leithead *et al.* dismiss this as concern stating ‘*since the X-rotor concept is for offshore deployment, noise is not considered to be an issue*’ (2019, p. 2). Though the noise will not affect most people, it could possibly affect wildlife behaviour of sea animals. In this regard, the experts’ desire of reduced bird collisions just may be addressed by the noise level of these secondary rotors into which bird may fly and die. It is thought that maybe the noise levels might be high enough to discourage birds from flying too close to the secondary rotor blades. This is being examined within the X-ROTOR project and a future deliverable will report on potential impact of noise and provide actionable recommendations to mitigate such impact.

Though the industry respondents did not think the option of a **fixed or floating** foundation all that important, ranked 13, the article does bring up the idea on three different occasions. A floating foundation will allow the developer to exploit the superior wind conditions that exist over open ocean. The X-ROTOR’s lower mass and lower centre of gravity than traditional HAWTs means that they may be more appropriate for floating foundations, or at least these foundations should be less costly than for the HAWTs (Borg and Collu, 2015).

Onshore requirements and **Effects on radio and radar** were not really discussed in the article. But because the X-ROTOR is half the size of the most comparable HAWT, the Vestas 6.2MW turbine discussed above, it should require less staging room and work area quayside. Additionally, because the maintenance boats do not have to be those large jack-up vessels, the bays themselves do not have to be as deep. As to the effects on electromagnetic waves, the differences are uncertain because it may not be related to the heights of the two contrasting structures.

4.2 Conclusion

This report, Deliverable 7.6 *Output of attribute matching*, used data collected through the project’s continuing engagement with industry stakeholders to identify and rank attributes important for potential purchasing decisions in which these stakeholders may have input. Though survey results for both groups were discussed along with a review of similar surveys in the literature to provide context, the evaluation for attribute matching is based solely with the industry survey responses as they are the potential buyers of this new offshore wind turbine. The attributes identified from the collected industry stakeholder data were compared with the features of the X-ROTOR derived from an analysis of the foundational overview text (Leithead *et al.*, 2019), which first described the concept. In this way the report assesses the extent to which the developing X-ROTOR design addresses those attributes which the industry stakeholders have deemed important to them.

As explained in Section 2, the methodology used in this work presented in this report was somewhat amended from that outlined in D7.5. Industry preferred attributes were determined following the sequencing exercise, and this was used in the attribute matching exercise. In quarter one 2023, the

engagement with industry stakeholders will continue¹¹ to gather additional responses, following which the postponed analytic hierarchy process will be conducted and thereafter the sequencing exercise revised. An updated iteration of the attribute matching will be with D7.7 report on economic impact.

¹¹ In part leveraging the in-person contacts facilitated by conferences such as EERA DeepWind scheduled for Jan 2023

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